

ISic4344

I.Sicily inscription 4344

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance

exact provenance unknown, but one of the three fragments has "Agira?"
on it

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia

dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/100, 05/134, 05/135

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G. 2014. Iscrizioni. In Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G., Tortorici, E.(eds.), *Il museo archeologico dell'Università di Catania. Collezione Libertini*. Acireale. pp. 170-173. At 170 no.233 fig.41

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